

Mapping the Landscape of Corporate Governance, ESG, and Financial Performance Research: A Bibliometric Analysis

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Abstract. Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) considerations have become central to sustainable business practices, yet the intersection of ESG, corporate governance, and financial performance remains fragmented in the literature. This study presents a bibliometric analysis of publications from the Scopus database between 2003 and 2025, focusing on research related to the ESG, corporate governance, and financial performance in the fields of accounting, banking, and finance. Using VOSviewer and the Bibliometrix R package, keyword co-occurrence, bibliographic coupling, and co-citation analyses were conducted to map the intellectual structure, thematic evolution, and global collaboration patterns of the field. The findings indicate that Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) and Sustainability represent the foundational and most established intellectual roots of ESG research, while Institutional Theory and corporate governance provide key theoretical explanations for how these themes have evolved and been operationalised across different contexts. Global research is highly Western-centric, dominated by the United Kingdom, United States, and Australia, though emerging economies contribute context-specific perspectives, particularly in banking, climate finance, and regional sustainability practices. Thematic mapping highlights conceptual gaps in foundational theories such as Legitimacy and Neo-Institutional Theory, while emerging and niche topics, such as Socially Responsible Investing, present opportunities for future exploration. The study highlights the need for greater theoretical coherence, enhanced international collaboration, and research into emerging digital technologies and circular economy practices to strengthen sustainable governance frameworks. Attention should be given to transparent, ethical, and sustainability-oriented governance systems, while suggesting the need for further empirical and theoretical research to deepen understanding in this evolving field of ESG–governance literature.

Keywords: ESG, circular, corporate governance, Socially Responsible Investing.

1 Introduction

Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) considerations have become central pillars of sustainable development, shaping how firms report, manage, and evaluate their economic and social impacts. ESG issues constitute the foundation of long-term value creation and sustainable growth, emphasising the need for responsible business behaviour and the balanced coexistence of economic systems with societal and environmental well-being [67]. Over the past decade, the concept of sustainability has

evolved substantially, supported by diverse frameworks and global initiatives that promote inclusive socio-economic progress and environmental protection [24]. The growing adoption of integrated reporting, sustainability disclosure standards, and the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) has contributed to a significant expansion of the scientific literature in accounting, finance, and corporate reporting [10, 22, 56, 69].

As organisations increasingly recognise the strategic importance of ESG performance, scholars have also highlighted the link between ESG disclosure and enhanced financial outcomes. Studies such as Chen and Xie [13] demonstrate that transparent ESG practices can strengthen firm performance, reputation, and overall corporate responsibility. However, the implementation of SDG-related disclosure introduces both opportunities and challenges for organisations, requiring firms to integrate social responsibility, governance practices, and long-term environmental concerns into their business models. Despite the proliferation of research on ESG [22, 60], SDGs [2, 69], and financial performance [23], there remains a gap concerning a consolidated bibliometric assessment of how these themes intersect within the broader fields of accounting, auditing, and finance.

Recent global events - including rising environmental degradation, corporate misconduct, and financial fraud - have further intensified interest in responsible governance and sustainable reporting practices [49]. As a result, ESG has become a rapidly growing field of academic studies. Several bibliometric studies have examined aspects of ESG research: Khan [35] combined bibliometric and meta-analysis to assess ESG and firm performance; Senadheera et al. [60] identified the current and future directions of ESG scholarship; Galletta et al. [26] mapped ESG research in the banking sector; Gao et al. [27] analysed 690 ESG publications in Scopus; and Li et al. [41] employed CiteSpace to investigate collaboration structures in top-tier ESG research. While these studies provide valuable insights, their scope is limited either by sector, geographical focus, or conceptual emphasis.

Moreover, Seow [61] emphasises that bibliometric outcomes may vary significantly across databases, reflecting differences in coverage and ESG's broad, context-specific definitions. In this regard, ESG has evolved from ethical and socially responsible investment practices into a multidimensional framework aligned with global sustainability priorities; however, existing Scopus-based bibliometric studies remain fragmented and lack a fully integrated synthesis of the field's intellectual structure and thematic evolution.

To address these gaps, this study utilises a dataset of publications extracted from the Scopus database for the period 2003 to 2025, focusing on the intersection of corporate governance, ESG performance, sustainability reporting, banking, and financial performance. Scopus provides comprehensive metadata across multiple fields, making it a valuable source for analysing publication patterns, thematic evolution, and collaborative networks. Through science mapping techniques, this study examines the structure of academic interest, identifies influential authors, journals, institutions, and countries, and analyses emerging knowledge clusters related to ESG, SDGs, corporate governance, and financial performance.

This study makes several key contributions. First, it provides an updated and holistic overview of research evolution in the domains of ESG, corporate governance, and financial performance by analysing trends derived from the Scopus database for the

period 2003 to 2025. Second, it identifies highly cited publications, thematic hotspots, and the intellectual structure of the field, including prominent discussions on ESG philosophy, and the relationship between ESG, corporate governance, CSR and performance. Third, the study traces the evolution of research themes over time to highlight potential future research pathways. Finally, the analysis provides valuable insights for academics, practitioners, and policymakers who seek to understand the changing landscape of corporate reporting, sustainable finance, and governance practices. Viewed through the lens of Society 5.0, the findings emphasise how ESG-driven sustainability reporting and sound corporate governance mechanisms contribute to transparent value creation, responsible performance, and societal well-being.

The remainder of this paper is organised as follows. Section 2 reviews the relevant literature. Section 3 outlines the bibliometric methodology and data selection process. Section 4 presents the results and discussion. Section 5 concludes the study with implications and future research directions.

1.1 Review of Literature

In addition to being a new avenue for sustainable human development, ESG offers a fresh viewpoint on the opportunities and threats that businesses confront. The connections between ESG and corporate governance, risk, cost of capital, business operations, and corporate performance have been thoroughly established [67].

ESG impacts the system risk of organisations, notably for enterprises with stronger product differentiation [64]. The company's risk decreases with improved ESG performance [1]. Firms with higher ESG performance were more adaptable and did better during the 2008 financial crisis, suggesting that ESG performance might enhance an organization's capacity to mitigate risk [6, 12, 42].

Organisations with good ESG performance have a wider range of investors than those with poor ESG performance [20] and are less likely to be sued, which ultimately results in lower capital costs [32]. One of the most contentious topics and one that has been extensively studied is how ESG affects firm performance or firm value. Existing research primarily examines whether ESG and firm performance or firm value are positively or negatively correlated based on various performance or value metrics.

2 Methodology

Research on corporate governance and sustainability has increasingly employed bibliometric analysis to derive original findings. Originally proposed by Pritchard [55], bibliometric analysis is a well-established quantitative method for tracking and measuring academic literature and has been widely used to explore the growth and intellectual structure of research fields [40, 33, 30]. This approach enables researchers to visualise the evolution of a discipline, identify influential authors and leading journals, and map emerging themes and trends.

In this study, bibliometric techniques were applied to accounting, banking and finance literature, focusing on corporate governance, ESG, and financial performance. The Scopus database was selected due to its extensive coverage of peer-reviewed outputs, including journal articles, books, reviews, and conference proceedings, as well

as its reliable citation networks and detailed author affiliation data [19, 47]. Bibliometric analysis allows researchers to examine publications, keywords, references, and productivity metrics of authors, institutions, and countries, providing insights into the current state and developmental trends of a research field [21, 51].

Following prior research [70], the authors used bibliometric tools for visual analysis, including VOSviewer and BibliometriX, an R package commonly applied for data analysis and visualization. The search keywords were: “Accountability,” “Financial performance,” “Banking sector,” “Profitability,” “Financial development,” “Corporate governance,” and “ESG”. These terms were required to appear in the title, abstract, keywords, or main text of the article.

The study explores ESG and related themes within accounting, auditing, and finance, using the banking sector as a contextual reference to illustrate their relevance to corporate governance and sustainability reporting [38]. In Society 5.0, banks act as the primary arbiters of sustainable value. Furthermore, a bank’s profitability is a prerequisite for its ability to fund social transformation as Society 5.0 requires resilient economic pillars [16]. The inclusion of ‘Accountability’ in the search string directly mirrors the Society 5.0 requirement for transparent governance systems. This ensures the analysis captures the shift from shareholder primacy to stakeholder trust. Although the ESG concept was formally introduced in the United Nations report *Who Cares Wins* [65], this study considers publications from 2003 to capture earlier conceptual developments in sustainability and corporate responsibility that later evolved into the ESG framework.

Figure 1: PRISMA Model adapted from *Page et al. (2021)*

This approach ensures the transitional period in which ESG-related themes were implicitly addressed is represented, providing a more comprehensive longitudinal analysis. The search was conducted in October 2025, and the inclusion criteria were as follows:

1. Articles indexed in Scopus under the categories of business, business finance, economics, and management; publications outside corporate governance, ESG, and financial performance fields were excluded.
2. Only peer-reviewed articles, book chapters and reviews were considered.
3. Publications were restricted to the English language.

3 Results, Analysis and Discussion of Findings

The keyword analysis is a method used to assess the relationship between research topics by counting the co-occurrence of keywords, which is beneficial in distinguishing research hotspots and research structure. The statistical items for keyword analysis in our study were author keywords. A network visualization of the co-occurrence of keywords using a full fractional method revealed a group of 83 keywords with a minimum of 3 co-occurrences. The colours in VOSviewer represent "clusters" groups of keywords that frequently appear together, representing distinct sub-fields or research themes. Figure 2 below illustrates clusters of keywords.

Figure 2. Clusters groups of keywords

3.1 The Core: CSR & Strategy (Blue Cluster)

For Over the past few decades, CSR, has been increasingly popular in both academia and business. Maheshwari et al. [43] examined dozens of CSR definitions, and while there are some differences in emphasis, scholars have generally acknowledged some common themes, such as the importance of stakeholder management [62] and addressing the need for social, economic, and environmental sustainability in line with the SDGs of the UN [48].

The performance of firms is positively correlated with CSR, according to research [50, 42]. The two conceptions' negative or non-association is also discussed by researchers [28, 53]. Certain researchers [7, 37] have also questioned the methodology used in numerous studies to examine the connection between CSR and firm performance.

As illustrated in Figure 2 above, CSR emerges as the largest and most central node within the blue cluster, highlighting its foundational role in the literature. In particular, academics have extensively examined whether socially responsible corporate behaviour contributes to improved financial outcomes, positioning CSR not only as an ethical imperative but also as a strategic driver of sustainable firm performance.

3.2 The Theoretical Framework (Purple/Orange Area)

According to Institutional Theory, an institution is defined by its formal rules and informal norms, including cultural norms, which shape organizational behaviour [39]. Through coercive isomorphism, Institutional Theory also accounts for externally imposed rules and standards that organizations are expected to follow within a given

environment [18]. The adoption of the SDGs promoted globally to address social and environmental challenges is a prominent example of such institutional standards influencing corporate practices.

Research on CSR that draws on Institutional Theory, particularly in the tradition of organizational (sociological) institutionalism [46, 18, 5], has accelerated substantially in recent years and is now one of the most frequently applied frameworks for studying corporate sustainability.

As indicated by the purple/orange cluster in Figure 2, the key nodes: “Institutional Theory,” “corporate governance,” and “institutional framework” suggest that researchers primarily use Institutional Theory to explain why companies adopt sustainable practices. The cluster’s strong connections to developing countries highlight that external pressures, including regulatory requirements and cultural expectations, are particularly influential in shaping CSR adoption in these contexts. Corporate governance structures mediate these pressures, translating institutional expectations into concrete organizational practices.

3.3 The Macro/Policy Perspective (Green Cluster)

SDG 17 on global partnerships represents a novel approach by explicitly designating a role for businesses in sustainable development, whereas previous UN statements primarily emphasized the responsibilities of governments. Many SDGs directly relate to socioeconomic human rights, particularly concerning human welfare and the provision of public goods, such as water, healthcare, and education.

According to Di Nardo et al. [17], there is significant overlap between the objectives of Political Corporate Social Responsibility (PCSR) and the SDGs. In particular, SDG 17 encourages businesses to strengthen partnerships for sustainable development and to support governments in achieving SDGs 1–16, which are traditionally viewed as the responsibility of states. A core principle of PCSR theory is the potential for businesses to address institutional gaps and contribute to the provision of public goods [59].

In practice, numerous businesses already make meaningful contributions that advance human rights. For instance, pharmaceutical companies facilitate access to essential medicines, supporting the right to health [11, 31], while water companies contribute to the right to water [66]. Similarly, vocational and technical skill-development programs promote the right to education [15]. These examples demonstrate that businesses can play a pivotal role in supporting policy objectives aligned with human rights.

3.4 Context & Sector Specifics (Yellow/Red/Mixed)

While many sectors respond to sustainability due to external stakeholder pressure [57], banks have increasingly taken a proactive role. They engage in CSR and sustainability initiatives to create value, enhance public image [45], and improve customer outcomes [8]. As their reputation depends on socially responsible activities [54], banks often rank highly on international CSR indices [9].

Although traditionally seen as environmentally benign, banks influence almost all industrial sectors through financing and thus bear indirect environmental responsibility

[44, 68]. They can promote sustainability by adopting eco-friendly technologies, products, and procedures [58] and by guiding firms toward responsible practices.

In Bangladesh, studies show mixed adoption of green banking. Commercial banks have implemented environmentally friendly policies, while state-owned and specialized banks lag [34, 36]. Islamic banks also contribute through energy savings and resource preservation [63], highlighting the need for mandating green banking.

Across Asia, China's green financial system, including green bonds and fintech initiatives exemplifies the integration of sustainability into banking. Green finance is expanding, though challenges remain in regulation, private sector engagement, and project allocation [4].

As Figure 3 shows, research focuses on emerging economies, particularly China and Bangladesh, and emphasizes the banking sector's central role in sustainability, green finance, and ethical banking.

3.5 Structural Metrics

The relationship between CSR and firm financial performance is among the most extensively studied topics in CSR research [25], reflecting the significant resources companies increasingly allocate to CSR initiatives. Al-Malkawi and Javaid [3] found that CSR in the form of Zakat contributions positively influenced the financial performance of 107 Saudi Arabian firms from 2004 to 2013, suggesting a win-win strategy that benefits society while enhancing profitability and firm value. Similarly, Choi et al. [14] and Hasan et al. [29] demonstrated that CSR activities helped protect firm value during the COVID-19, improving stock returns and stakeholder engagement.

Referring to the above figure, large nodes representing "CSR" and "Sustainable Development" indicate these are well-established and heavily studied topics, while smaller nodes such as "green economy" and "integrated reporting" point to emerging or niche areas. The thick link between "CSR" and "Financial Performance" highlights that this specific relationship remains the most researched hypothesis within the dataset.

3.6 Bibliographic coupling

We used a fractional counting method with a minimum citation per country of 2 and a minimum of two documents per country. Bibliographic coupling reveals the global intellectual structure by linking nations that build on the same literature, while fractional counting ensures a fair comparison by weighing multi-country collaborations proportionally so that results are not skewed. The applied thresholds serve to filter out "noise," ensuring the analysis focuses only on countries with a consistent and meaningful contribution to the field.

Figure 3 reveals stratas that are anchored by the United Kingdom, the United States, and Australia. The size of the United Kingdom's node suggest it functions as the primary intellectual "bridge" in this field, filtering and disseminating theoretical frameworks between the North American tradition (represented by the yellow cluster with the USA) and the Commonwealth or Asia-Pacific regions. This dominance indicates that the foundational literature is largely Western-centric. Consequently, researchers in peripheral nodes are likely analysing their local contexts through lenses

polished in these central Western nations, which raises important questions about the applicability of those theories to developing economies.

Figure 3. Global Research Landscape

The clustering pattern further exposes distinct "invisible colleges" where countries are grouped not merely by geography, but by shared intellectual lineages and research priorities. For instance, the red cluster connecting Australia with developing nations like Malaysia, Indonesia, Bangladesh, and Tunisia suggests that despite vast economic differences, researchers in these countries are grappling with similar issues. Similarly,

Country Collaboration Map

the blue cluster involving Pakistan, Saudi Arabia, and Romania indicates a shared theoretical approach to issues, specific to emerging markets or Islamic finance contexts. This clustering proves that the field is not a monolith; rather, it is composed of distinct regional conversations that are overlapping but conceptually unique.

Figure 4. Country Collaboration Map

We also utilised the Biblmetrix module to create a country collaboration map. Combined with the previous figure, the Anglo and European countries clusters show mature interconnected core topics. However, the presence of emerging clusters in the periphery signals a divergence where new, context-specific literature is beginning to form. This map serves as evidence that while the "rules" of the field are written in the UK and US, the most dynamic application of these rules is happening in the Global South. It validates the need for research to prevent the field from becoming an echo of Western ideologies.

The authors have also developed the co-citation network of the cited sources, using the fractional counting method with a minimum of 5 citations. This approach ensures a balanced mapping of the field's intellectual structure by neutralizing the bias of long reference lists via fractional counting, while the threshold filters out noise to isolate only the most stable and impactful connections.

Figure 5. Co-citation network of the cited sources

The map is defined by two major, tightly knit knowledge bases: the Accounting Cluster (Red) and the Organization and Management Cluster (Green). The red cluster indicates a strong theoretical reliance on critical and sociological accounting literature. The green cluster, however, contributes the core theoretical lens of organizational behaviour and structure, thereby linking the accounting foundations to broader management concepts.

The Finance, Ethics, and Economics Cluster (Blue) suggests that ethics serves as a primary bridging discipline with the intersection of ethical principles and tangible financial and economic outcomes, rather than treating ethics as a separate philosophical discussion. Moreover, journals like the Academy of Management Journal reinforce general management theory by connecting the organizational and ethical clusters.

Structurally, the network shows a flow from the Micro to the Macro. The left side is dominated by journals focusing on technical and micro-level reporting (Accounting), while the network stretches out to the right toward the International Governance Cluster (Cyan), ranging from the internal accounting practices of firms to global regulatory frameworks.

The Bibliometrix module from the R Studio software was employed to create a thematic map based on the author's keywords. We used a minimum cluster frequency of 5 (per thousand documents) and a walk trap algorithm. This method is important because it relies on accurate author-defined keywords to isolate established, core research themes using the frequency threshold, ensuring the resulting thematic map is robust and structurally clear.

Figure 6. Thematic map based on the author's keywords

The thematic map illustrated in Figure 6 categorizes themes based on their Relevance degree (Centrality) on the X-axis and their Development degree (Density) on the Y-axis. The Motor Themes (Top Right Quadrant: High Centrality, High Density) represent CSR and Sustainability clusters as highly mature and central pillars. Additionally, the presence of Institutional Context, Climate Change, and Greenwashing in this quadrant indicates the research has moved beyond defining CSR and is highly focused on its complex, real-world application, institutional pressures, and contemporary issues. Themes like Sustainability Reporting and the specific setting of Bangladesh show a high level of consolidation around reporting mechanisms and practical, geographic applications.

The Basic Themes (Bottom Right Quadrant: High Centrality, Low Density) represent fundamental themes yet their internal coherence is low. Key concepts here include Sustainable Development, CSR Disclosure, Legitimacy, and Neo-Institutional Theory within the literature by identifying the main clusters of research and examining their temporal evolution and reconfiguration over time. Their low density suggests a lack of consensus, standardization, or structural consolidation in how these foundational theories and concepts are applied or measured across different studies. The field is highly applied (as seen in the Motor Themes), but its fundamental theoretical underpinnings are underdeveloped, presenting a significant opportunity for future work to unify and solidify these core theoretical frameworks.

The Niche Themes are well-developed and conceptually coherent but remain specialized and largely disconnected from the field's main debates. Topics like the COVID-19 crisis and mining industry motivations confirm that research quickly consolidates around specific empirical contexts or sudden, event-driven phenomena, but these findings do not broadly influence the central CSR/Sustainability discussion. The presence of philosophical terms like paradox and cruelty confirms that specialized theoretical debates exist but are currently isolated from mainstream.

The Emerging or Declining Themes are currently marginal to the research focus. The cluster around Socially Responsible Investing (SRI) suggests that while relevant, it is not the primary academic mechanism, perhaps being absorbed into the broader ESG Disclosure theme (which is closer to the center). The research on the link between performance and sustainability is also weakly defined here, indicating findings have become too fragmented or inconclusive to form a stable theme. Thus, the empirical

application of CSR and Sustainability remain strong, but its main weakness is the lack of conceptual coherence and standardization around the highly central theoretical foundations of Legitimacy and Neo-Institutional theory.

4 Conclusion and Recommendations

The purpose of this study was to present the development of Corporate Governance, ESG, and Financial Performance research, and to discuss research connected to these issues. A bibliometric analysis of the relevant research themes was carried out in this study. The VOS viewer and the Bibliometrix module from the R Studio software were used to create the maps after the data were obtained from the Scopus database. However, different results might have been obtained from data gathered at different times or from different databases. Clustering and future trends can be examined using bibliographic coupling, keyword co-occurrence, and co-citations.

The bibliometric analysis reveals that research on corporate governance, ESG, and sustainability is highly developed around core themes such as CSR and Sustainability, which dominate both keyword co-occurrence and thematic maps. Institutional Theory, corporate governance, and sector-specific applications highlight the theoretical frameworks and contextual diversity guiding the field. At the global level, research remains Western-centric, with the United Kingdom, United States, and Australia acting as central intellectual hubs, while emerging economies contribute context-specific insights, particularly in banking, climate finance, and regional sustainability practices.

Thematic mapping indicates a mature empirical focus on CSR and Sustainability, but also identifies conceptual gaps in foundational theories like Legitimacy and Neo-Institutional Theory. Niche and emerging themes, such as Socially Responsible Investing, highlight areas for further exploration, while the fragmentation of basic theoretical concepts points to a need for greater coherence and standardization. Overall, the field is empirically robust but theoretically uneven, presenting opportunities to strengthen its conceptual foundations and bridge global and local research perspectives.

4.1 Limitations and Future Studies

To assist academics, policymakers, and practitioners in developing more resilient and inclusive corporate governance models aligned with global sustainability goals, this study identifies key authors, institutions, and thematic clusters. Future research should prioritize the integration of emerging technologies and international collaboration while deepening the examination of the socioeconomic impacts of corporate governance practices to advance sustainable development. In particular, further studies could explore the application of digital technologies and artificial intelligence in ESG analytics, the role of blockchain in enhancing transparency, and the implications of digital transformation for sustainable governance frameworks.

Furthermore, further empirical studies on the convergence of circular economy practices and corporate governance are required in order to produce universal governance standards that can be applied to different legal frameworks. One such limitation of this study includes its reliance on Scopus bibliometric data, which may lead to the exclusion of relevant studies from other databases. Furthermore, the focus

on English-language publications may overlook significant contributions from non-English-speaking regions, limiting the findings' global applicability. Future studies that address these issues will provide a deeper understanding of the dynamic interaction between sustainability and corporate governance.

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